

Barrels from the Skaftö shipwreck

by
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In the interest of access to data and to enable researchers to utilise this material in the future, all measurements are submitted to the Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD, www.dendrochronology.eu).

A total of 23 parts from barrels, found in the Skaftö shipwreck were submitted for analysis. After initial examination of these it was found that two samples (T8 oak & T10 ash) contained too few tree-rings for a dendrochronological analysis, and these two were not examined further. Of the remaining 21 samples all are of *Quercus sp.*, oak, except one, which is of *Fraxinus Excelsior*, ash.

The 20 oak samples are dated (see fig. 1). The tree-ring series from some of the barrel parts are so alike that the artefacts might come from the same tree.

Tree 1: Three staves (T12, T22 and T23) can come from a single tree, and thus might be from the same barrel. Sapwood is preserved on two of these staves. Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree that was used to make these staves was felled around the period AD 1429-42.

Tree 2: As many as five barrel parts can be assigned to tree 2. These include two barrel head halves (T5 & T7) and three staves (T13, T15 & T21). This probably again indicates that these are from the same barrel on the ship. Possible bark edge was preserved on one of the barrel head halves, but this could not be confirmed with certainty. The tree for the barrel was felled in AD 1439 or shortly after.

Tree 3: Two staves might also have been made from a single tree (T17 & T24). Both of these have sapwood preserved. Accounting for missing sapwood, the felling date for tree 3 can be estimated to be within the period AD 1436-50.

Tree 4: Finally two additional barrel staves (T18 & T19) might come from the same tree. One of these has the boundary between heartwood and sapwood preserved. The felling date for the tree that was used to make these staves took place within the period AD 1442-57.

Fig. 1. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the barrel part from the Skaftö wreck.

The tree-ring series from the remaining samples match well with the material as a whole (see table 1) except for one barrel head (T6) which is probably from the inner rings of a quite long-lived tree, which is not unusual in material of this kind. The estimates for the felling dates for the trees that the remaining barrel parts were made from fall within the range of that of the four single trees described above. It is possible that the barrels are from a single felling event, but the dendrochronological evidence cannot confirm this definitively. There is a possibility that two or more felling events are represented in the material: one for example around c. 1439 and another in the 1440s.

As indicated at the left column in table 1, just one mean curve (Z084M001) is made, including tree-ring series from the barrel parts that match best together.

		Z084005a	Z084013a	Z084007a	Z084015a	Z084021a	Z084022a	Z084012a	Z084023a	Z084003a	Z084004a	Z084016a	Z084020a	Z084014a	Z084017a	Z084024a	Z084018a	Z084019a	Z084025a	Z084002a	Z084006a		
Mean curve Z084M001	Same tree (tree 2)	Z084005a	*	13,11	12,32	12,46	12,65	-	-	-	-	4,61	3,57	-	-	3,57	5,51	4,02	4,44	4,31	3,02	\	
		Z084013a	13,11	*	9,08	12,86	11,92	-	-	-	-	4,93	4,36	3,03	-	4,16	4,84	3,64	4,33	3,36	3,52	\	
		Z084007a	12,32	9,08	*	17,61	11,34	3,57	-	-	-	4,45	3,97	-	-	-	-	3,3	3,89	3,46	3,64	\	
		Z084015a	12,46	12,86	17,61	*	15,79	3,67	-	3,11	-	5,76	3,85	-	-	-	4,46	3,08	3,43	3,73	-	\	
		Z084021a	12,65	11,92	11,34	15,79	*	4,5	3,25	3,45	-	5,3	3,34	-	-	-	4,47	3,34	3,68	3,45	3,08	\	
	Same tree (tree 1)	Z084022a	-	-	3,57	3,67	4,5	*	13,51	13,86	3,66	3,12	3,84	-	3,2	-	3,15	3,15	3,15	-	-	\	
		Z084012a	-	-	-	-	3,25	13,51	*	16,35	4,97	5,08	4,07	4,55	5,36	4,21	5,14	3,93	4,37	-	-	\	
		Z084023a	-	-	-	3,11	3,45	13,86	16,35	*	4,58	4,64	4,06	3,7	3,92	3,33	3,88	3,36	3,71	-	-	\	
		Z084003a	-	-	-	-	-	3,66	4,97	4,58	*	5,97	5,04	3,64	3,52	-	3,41	-	-	-	-	\	
		Z084004a	4,61	4,93	4,45	5,76	5,3	3,12	5,08	4,64	5,97	*	5,46	4,05	3,07	4,19	4,9	3,13	-	-	-	3,73	
		Z084016a	3,57	4,36	3,97	3,85	3,34	3,84	4,07	4,06	5,04	5,46	*	6,19	4,36	4,21	4,45	-	3,25	3,4	4,12	\	
		Z084020a	-	3,03	-	-	-	-	4,55	3,7	3,64	4,05	6,19	*	5,6	7,18	6,98	6,66	7,54	7,58	3,1	\	
		Z084014a	-	-	-	-	-	3,2	5,36	3,92	3,52	3,07	4,36	5,6	*	10,39	8,86	5,71	5,23	5,6	-	\	
		Tree 3	Z084017a	3,57	4,16	-	-	-	-	4,21	3,33	-	4,19	4,21	7,18	10,39	*	13,78	6,78	7,05	7,12	5,36	\
			Z084024a	5,51	4,84	-	4,46	4,47	3,15	5,14	3,88	3,41	4,9	4,45	6,98	8,86	13,78	*	7,59	7,42	8,38	4,41	\
	Tree 4	Z084018a	4,02	3,64	3,3	3,08	3,34	3,15	3,93	3,36	-	3,13	-	6,66	5,71	6,78	7,59	*	17,63	8,35	-	\	
		Z084019a	4,44	4,33	3,89	3,43	3,68	3,15	4,37	3,71	-	-	3,25	7,54	5,23	7,05	7,42	17,63	*	8,94	-	\	
		Z084025a	4,31	3,36	3,46	3,73	3,45	-	-	-	-	-	3,4	7,58	5,6	7,12	8,38	8,35	8,94	*	-	\	
		Z084002a	3,02	3,52	3,64	-	3,08	-	-	-	-	-	4,12	3,1	-	5,36	4,41	-	-	-	*	\	
		Z084006a	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	3,73	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	*	

Table 1. Barrels from the Skaftö wreck, Sweden, showing the correlation (t-value) between each barrel part and each other. The dash (-) indicates a t-value of less than 3.00. The backslash (\) signifies an overlap of less than 30 years.

Provenance

When the tree-ring curves from the barrels from the Skaftö wreck are compared with a wide range of chronologies from Northern Europe the best statistical agreement (highest t-values) appear with oak material that is known to come from the southeastern Baltic region. The material fits therefore perfectly with the constantly expanding story of the trade in timber and other wares from the Southern Baltic region. The Danish Sound Toll Records attest to trade through Øresund, and the dendrochronological dataset confirms this traffic, in that shipwrecks with planks in their cargo, barrels, painted panels etc from the period are often shown to be made from Southern Baltic oak (see for example Wazny 2002, Daly 2007 or Daly & Läänelaid 2012). The barrels from the Skaftö wreck are dated against a range of these objects, as can be seen from the table of correlation (table 2). A precise provenance for this southern Baltic material is not as yet identified, but it is taken to come from regions along the south and southeastern Baltic coast or further inland.

Filenames	-	-	Tree 2 Z084 1029	Mean curve Z084 M001	Single Z084 002a	Single Z084 006a	
-	start	dates	AD1319	AD1152	AD1355	AD1141	
-	dates	end	AD1438	AD1437	AD1437	AD1260	
00751M01	AD1113	AD1463	6,85	8,16	6,47	4,06	Vejdyb ship (Daly 1997)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	3,96	8,04	-	3,46	Copper Ship Wainscot (Wazny pers comm.)
HEADSx11	AD1304	AD1521	3,38	8,03	5,47	\	Stirling heads Baltic (Crone pers comm.)
se613m01	AD1197	AD1464	6,62	7,61	4,06	4,09	Hull Blaydes Staithe (Tyers pers comm.)
Z054m001	AD1235	AD1448	3,92	7,10	3,90	\	Ostsee VII planks (Daly 2010)
OM040004	AD1156	AD1597	6,49	6,38	6,69	3,48	Baltic 1 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
stirlingdoors	AD1270	AD1524	4,63	6,28	4,52	\	Stirlingdoors (Crone pers comm.)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	-	6,24	\	4,36	Hull boards Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm.)
SM100003	AD1135	AD1711	-	5,77	-	3,26	Ystad (Bartholin pers comm)
02071M01	AD1126	AD1414	-	5,65	-	4,59	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	-	5,49	-	\	Baltic 2 (Tyers pers comm.)
PUCKM002	AD1134	AD1329	\	5,48	\	4,92	Puck (Wazny pers comm.)
Z0700019	AD1238	AD1436	4,17	5,31	3,98	\	Bouts painting Madonna med barnet (Daly 2011)
0EQKTVM001	AD1295	AD1549	-	5,16	-	\	Tallinn Money-lenders (Daly & Läänelaid 2012)
CLS2000	AD1110	AD1393	-	5,13	-	4,47	Hull Chapel Lane (Tyers pers comm.)
0628002M	AD1225	AD1445	3,52	5,06	-	-	Torun Joh Kir (Wazny pers comm.)
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	-	4,80	-	5,30	Gdansk (Wazny pers comm.)
P671001M	AD980	AD1347	\	4,53	\	5,31	Elblag (Wazny pers comm.)
DM100008	AD457	AD1723	-	4,35	-	3,63	Lübeck (Hamburg University)

Table 2. Barrels from the Skaftö wreck, Sweden, showing the results of the calculation of correlation between the tree-ring curves from the barrel parts and diverse site and master chronologies from Northern Europe. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values. The dash (-) indicates a t-value of less than 3.00. The backslash (\) signifies an overlap of less than 30 years.

Analysis

For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t-value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed. For calculation of the felling date for the trees used to make these artefacts a sapwood statistic developed by Wazny (1990) for the Southern Baltic region is utilised. Here oaks have an average of 15 (-6 +9) sapwood rings.

Literature

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Catalogue

Catalogue format:

Filename
 Title and sample number
 Tree species (QUSP = *Quercus sp.*, oak, PISY = *Pinus sp.*, pine, FREX = *Fraxinus Excelsior*, ash) and number of years measured
 Chronological position of the tree-ring curve
 Number of sapwood years, presence of bark
 Felling date

Z084002a

Skaftö wreck barrel head T2
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 83 years length
 Dated AD 1355 to AD 1437
 4 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 206.10 Sensitivity 0.22
 Interpretation AD 1442-57

Z084003a

Skaftö wreck barrel fragment T3
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 181 years length
 Dated AD 1257 to AD 1437
 17 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 55.69 Sensitivity 0.20
 Interpretation AD 1437-44

Z084004a

Skaftö wreck barrel head T4
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 262 years length
 Dated AD 1152 to AD 1413
 0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 71.67 Sensitivity 0.19
 Interpretation after AD 1423

Z084005a

Skaftö wreck barrel head T5
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 120 years length
 Dated AD 1319 to AD 1438
 12 sapwood rings and possible bark surface
 Average ring width 168.90 Sensitivity 0.25
 Interpretation AD 1439?

Z084006a

Skaftö wreck barrel head T6
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 120 years length
 Dated AD 1141 to AD 1260
 0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 83.40 Sensitivity 0.28
 Interpretation after AD 1275

Z084007a

Skaftö wreck barrel head T7
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 98 years length
 Dated AD 1338 to AD 1435
 13 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 159.42 Sensitivity 0.21
 Interpretation AD 1435-46

T8 barrel head, QUSP oak, too few rings, not measured.

Z084009a

Skaftö wreck barrel plank T9

Raw Ring-width FREX data of 52 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 285.08 Sensitivity 0.23

T10 barrel head, FREX ash, too few rings, not measured.

Z084012a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T12

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 125 years length

Dated AD 1291 to AD 1415

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 139.49 Sensitivity 0.15

Interpretation after AD 1425

Z084013a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T13

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 88 years length

Dated AD 1349 to AD 1436

9 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 179.23 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation AD 1437-51

Z084014a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T14

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 127 years length

Dated AD 1309 to AD 1435

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 126.13 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation after AD 1445

Z084015a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T15

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 79 years length

Dated AD 1345 to AD 1423

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 189.90 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation after AD 1433

Z084016a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T16

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 151 years length

Dated AD 1281 to AD 1431

18 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 105.69 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation AD 1432-7

Z084017a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T17

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 119 years length

Dated AD 1314 to AD 1432

7 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 138.61 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation AD 1434-49

Z084018a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T18
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 103 years length
 Dated AD 1331 to AD 1433
 0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 156.86 Sensitivity 0.24
 Interpretation after AD 1442

Z084019a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T19
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 111 years length
 Dated AD 1323 to AD 1433
 0 sapwood rings h/s boundary
 Average ring width 165.42 Sensitivity 0.23
 Interpretation AD 1442-57?

Z084020a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T20
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 107 years length
 Dated AD 1319 to AD 1425
 0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 166.36 Sensitivity 0.23
 Interpretation after AD 1435

Z084021a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T21
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 78 years length
 Dated AD 1356 to AD 1433
 7 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 172.53 Sensitivity 0.20
 Interpretation AD 1435-50

Z084022a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T22
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 88 years length
 Dated AD 1341 to AD 1428
 10 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 129.75 Sensitivity 0.14
 Interpretation AD 1429-42

Z084023a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T23
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 107 years length
 Dated AD 1320 to AD 1426
 9 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 141.59 Sensitivity 0.15
 Interpretation AD 1426-41

Z084024a

Skaftö wreck barrel stave T24
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 118 years length
 Dated AD 1318 to AD 1435
 9 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 149.58 Sensitivity 0.21
 Interpretation AD 1436-50

Z084025a
 Skaftö wreck barrel stave T25
 Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 116 years length
 Dated AD 1318 to AD 1433
 7 sapwood rings and no bark surface
 Average ring width 157.84 Sensitivity 0.19
 Interpretation AD 1435-50

filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	group	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
Z084002a	Skaftö wreck barrel head T2 QUSP	83	AD 1355	AD 1437	R	G	4	-			S1	AD 1442-57
Z084003a	Skaftö wreck barrel fragment T3 QUSP	181	AD 1257	AD 1437	R	G	17	-			-	AD 1437-44
Z084004a	Skaftö wreck barrel head T4 QUSP	262	AD 1152	AD 1413	R	G	-	-			H1	after AD 1423
Z084005a	Skaftö wreck barrel head T5 QUSP	120	AD 1319	AD 1438	R	G	12	Bark?			-	AD 1439?
Z084006a	Skaftö wreck barrel head T6 QUSP	120	AD 1141	AD 1260	R	G	-	-			H6	after AD 1275
Z084007a	Skaftö wreck barrel head T7 QUSP	98	AD 1338	AD 1435	R	G	13	-			-	AD 1435-46
	T8 QUSP few rings not measured											
Z084009a	Skaftö wreck barrel plank T9 FREX	52			R	G	-	-			H1	Undated
	T10 FREX few rings not measured											
Z084012a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T12 QUSP	125	AD 1291	AD 1415	R	G	-	-			H1	after AD 1425
Z084013a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T13 QUSP	88	AD 1349	AD 1436	R	G	9	-			S1	AD 1437-51
Z084014a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T14 QUSP	127	AD 1309	AD 1435	O	G	-	-			H1	after AD 1445
Z084015a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T15 QUSP	79	AD 1345	AD 1423	R	G	-	-			H1	after AD 1433
Z084016a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T16 QUSP	151	AD 1281	AD 1431	R	G	18	-			S1	AD 1432-7
Z084017a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T17 QUSP	119	AD 1314	AD 1432	T	G	7	-			S1	AD 1434-49
Z084018a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T18 QUSP	103	AD 1331	AD 1433	R	G	-	-			-	after AD 1442
Z084019a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T19 QUSP	111	AD 1323	AD 1433	R	G	h/s	-			-	AD 1442-57
Z084020a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T20 QUSP	107	AD 1319	AD 1425	O	G	-	-			H1	after AD 1435
Z084021a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T21 QUSP	78	AD 1356	AD 1433	R	G	7	-			-	AD 1435-50
Z084022a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T22 QUSP	88	AD 1341	AD 1428	R	G	10	-			S1	AD 1429-42
Z084023a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T23 QUSP	107	AD 1320	AD 1426	T	G	9	-			-	AD 1426-41
Z084024a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T24 QUSP	118	AD 1318	AD 1435	R	G	9	-			S1	AD 1436-50
Z084025a	Skaftö wreck barrel stave T25 QUSP	116	AD 1318	AD 1433	R	G	7	-			S1	AD 1435-50
Z0841019	Skaftö wreck barrel same tree 12 22 23 (tree 1)	138	AD 1291	AD 1428			10	-				
Z0841029	Skaftö wreck barrel same tree 5 7 13 15 21 (tree 2)	120	AD 1319	AD 1438			13	Bark?				
Z0841039	Skaftö wreck barrel same tree 17 24 (tree 3)	122	AD 1314	AD 1435			9	-				
Z0841049	same tree 18 19 (tree 4)	111	AD 1323	AD 1433			h/s					
Z084M001	Skaftö wreck barrels 9 timber mean QUSP	286	AD 1152	AD 1437								

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
 Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.